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Stress in the Midst of the Pandemic- A Study among College Students from the North East of India

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *Stress is said to be a pre-cursor to several mental health issues including suicide. India has a massive youth population but also the highest suicide rate among youth in the world. This is why it is important to examine the mental health and in particular, the stress levels of youth and the stress levels of migrant youth specifically, that too in the midst of the pandemic. The objective of the study is to measure the levels of stress among college students from the North East living in Bengaluru and Puducherry.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *Total of 73 migrant youth from the North East living in Bengaluru and Puducherry were selected using convenience sampling. The perceived stress scale developed by Cohen et. al. (1993) was used to measure the level of stress.*

Findings/Results: *Based on the results, it can be stated that a little less than half of the total respondents (45.2 per cent) have an above average level of stress. There was a positive correlation found between the age of the respondents and their level of stress and a statistically significant difference in the mean score of stress of the respondents across their employment status.*

Originality/Value: *An understanding of the level of stress of North Eastern migrant college students during the pandemic.*

Paper Type: *Empirical*

Keywords: *Migrant College Students, Stress, Mental Health, North East*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Stress is often defined as the body's response to a potential threat or change from either forces within our body or from outside it [1]. Since life is filled with unexpected events, one can state that stress is a part and parcel of life itself. Although this may be true, it is also unnerving, and studies indicate that there is a strong connection between stress and other health issues including insomnia, which in turn leads to further health issues [2]. Furthermore, stressful life events can negatively impact the nervous system as well [3]. This is because the stress system which controls the stress mechanism is present in the central nervous system [4]. It is therefore not surprising that there is also a well-established link between exposure to stressors and depression with the exposure to stressors predicting reoccurrence of depression [5]. All these factors highlight the importance of examining this issue further and that too in the context of youth and in particular migrant youth and youth in general. Youth who migrate to a new state or country often need to make adjustments to fit into their new local environment and culture [6]. This is specifically true in the case of health-related issues. Bener(2017) [7] in his study has noted that about 80 percent of the migrant workers did not have medical insurance. In the context of migrant youth in particular, it appears that

migrant youth who have previously experienced trauma, display more peer problems and fewer pro-social behaviours[8]. This fact adds to the need for acculturation for migrant youth as it has been shown to be highly beneficial for their mental health [9]. With regard to rural to urban migration among the youth in particular, it appears to be a growing trend, not only in India, but also in other developing countries such as Uganda [10].

One may assume that those youth who migrate to urban areas are fully self-sufficient and do not require support from their families. This in fact may not be true as observed by Heckert(2015) [11] in the Haitian context, wherein the migrant youth were receiving financial support rather than sending remittances. The same could be concluded for migrant youth in India who have re-located to a metropolitan city like Bengaluru for education. In India, there is also a growing concern about the issue of internal brain drain wherein some states are losing out their best workers and students to other states that have better educational and job opportunities [12]. There is also another concerning trend of middle-class youth from India migrating to foreign countries to seek education and employment opportunities [2]. This is concerning because it again leads brain drain at a national level. These are however large-scale issues that require further investigation by further researchers. The present study is primarily focused on the youth who have already migrated internally to the city of Bengaluru and the Union Territory of Puducherry from the north eastern parts of India. It may be noted that the pandemic adds to complexity of the wellbeing aspect of these youth as the pandemic has left many youth without any structured support to help protect and promote their mental wellbeing [13].

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Migration has been closely associated with humankind ever since the dawn of human history. It must be noted though, the purpose and type of migration has undergone tremendous change over the years and accordingly, its impact on the human mind and body is also bound to change. Perhaps this is particularly true for migration from rural to urban areas. This is what Van Huy et al. (2010) [14] found in their study. They found that migrant labourers who migrated from rural to urban areas in Vietnam had physical, social, and financial stressors. Another aspect to consider whether mental health. In his article on the wellbeing of immigrant youth, Nolan (2010) [15] notes that the wellbeing of youth is closely associated with their socio-economic status and success. In another study by Soshani et al. (2015) [16], conducted in Steal among 448 adolescents, it was discovered that the migrant adolescents in the study had higher levels of mental health issues and engaged in risk behaviours more frequently than the native respondents. In some cases, the youth who migrate to another country or place are very young and yet are not accompanied by their parents or other family members. This is what was examined by Longobardi et al. (2017) [17] wherein they examined the provenance of post-traumatic stress among unaccompanied youth migrants (aged 16-17 years) in Italy, who had migrated from seven different nations. The researchers found that the level of posttraumatic stress, apart from other variables, among the respondents, was clearly above the clinical cut off point. Cardoso (2018) [18] in her study which involved examining the trauma symptoms among thirty unaccompanied migrant youth aged between 11-17 years, came across a similar finding. The results in her study indicated that a little more than half (56.7 per cent) of the total respondents met the criteria for post-traumatic stress disorder which indicated the seriousness of the problem. Noh and Moon. (2018) [19] in their article have pointed to the fact among the South Korean migrants in the United States, depression, anxiety, suicidal ideation has been linked with acculturative stress. It is important to note that it is not just the migration itself but also the manner in which the youth are received in this host nation which could make an important difference. In one recent study by Salas-wright et al. (2020) [20], conducted among 402 recently immigrated Venezuelan youth who had migrated to the United States, it was found that, negative context of reception was associated with substance use among the respondents.

3. RESEARCH GAP:

From the review of these and several other previous studies that have been highlighted in the full paper, the researchers identified three major areas that require further investigation and which the present study will dwell into:

1. Paucity of studies on north eastern migrant youth in India.
2. Paucity of studies on stress faced by this particular group of youth.

3. Paucity of studies that examine the stress related impact of the pandemic on this particular group of youth.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

Using the research gap, the researchers have derived the following objectives of the present study:

1. To describe the background characteristics of North Eastern migrant youth residing in Bengaluru and Pondicherry.
2. To measure the level of stress faced by the respondents.
3. To discover the relationship between age and stress scores of the respondents.
4. To test whether the employment status of the respondents during the pandemic is connected to their stress scores.

5. METHODOLOGY:

5.1 Research design:

The present study is exploratory in nature as there haven't been any studies of this nature concerning North Eastern Migrant youth in India.

5.2 Universe and Sample:

In the present study, the researchers have purposively selected Bengaluru and Puducherry as these are familiar to the researchers. Thus, north eastern migrant youth aged between 18-30 years living in these two places are the universe of the present study. Since the size of the universe is unknown, non-probability sampling in the form of convenience sampling was adopted to select 73 respondents who constitute the sample in the present study.

5.3 Tools of Data Collection:

The researchers employed a questionnaire with two parts for collecting data from the respondents. The first part contains questions regarding the background characteristics of the respondents whereas the second part contains the perceived stress scale developed by Cohen et. al. (1993). This being a standardised scale, the validity and reliability of the scale is well established.

6. HYPOTHESES:

1. H1- There is a statistically significant correlation between the age of the respondents and their stress scores.
2. H1- There is a statistically significant difference in the mean score of stress of the respondents across their status of employment.

7. RESULTS:

7.1 Background Characteristics:

The respondents in the present study hail from Meghalaya, Manipur, Nagaland, Assam, Sikkim, and Arunachal Pradesh. The average age of the respondents was found to be 22 years, with the youngest respondent being 18 years and the oldest respondent being 27 years of age. A huge majority of the total respondents (190 percent) are not working. A little more than two third of the total respondents (67 per cent) were able to return home during the pandemic.

7.2 Level of Stress:

Based on the results, it can be stated that a little less than half of the total respondents (45.2 per cent) have an above average level of stress.

8. NORMALITY:

Before performing the Pearson's correlation test, the normality was tested and it was found that both the variables in question- age of the respondents and their stress scores were normally distributed as observed here.

GRAPH /HISTOGRAM (NORMAL) = age.

Fig. 1: Test of normality for Pearson's Correlation

9. CORRELATION BETWEEN AGE AND STRESS:

Variables	Correlation value	Sig. (2 tailed)
Age & Stress	0.268	0.22 P<0.05

Table 1: Correlation between age and stress

The results of the Pearson’s correlation analysis (as seen in table 1) indicates the fact that there is a positive correlation between the age of the respondents and their stress scores. In other words, as the age of the respondent goes up so does their stress score. One possible reason for this finding is the looming pressure of the students to score well in exams so that they are able to find suitable jobs which have decreased due to the pandemic.

Thus, the alternate hypothesis (H1), that is *there is a statistically significant correlation between the age of the respondents and their stress scores*, is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

10. NORMALITY FOR T-TEST:

In order to perform the t- test, the normality of the residuals was tested and it was found that the data was normally

distributed as seen in the figure.

Fig. 2: Test of normality for t-test

11.T-TEST- EMPLOYMENT STATUS AND STRESS:

SL NO.	Variable	N	Satisfaction with Life (Mean score)
1	Employed	7	26.43
	Unemployed	66	22.48
	F Ratio	0.95	
	P value	0.043 (p<0.05)	

Table 2- Results of the t-test

An independent sample t test was conducted to examine whether there is any statistically significant difference in the mean score of stress of the respondents across their employment status. It may be noted that all the respondents in the present study who have stated that they are employed are part-timers.

From the results of the t-test (as seen in table 2), it is apparent that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean score of stress of the respondents across their employment status at a moderate level (p<0.05). Furthermore, the mean score of stress for part-time workers was higher than those who were not employed. One possible explanation of this finding is that those who are not working are students who are funded and supported by their parents sufficiently whereas those who are employed as part timers are self-dependent when it comes to meeting

their daily expenses and during the height of the pandemic when this data was collected, their jobs were at risk, possibly leading them to become more stressful as a result.

12. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

The results of t-test and the correlation analysis clearly highlight the need for intervention among migrant youth who are older and those who are dependent on their own job to meet their daily needs. The pandemic may be partly over. However, there is always a danger looming with regard to another variant emerging and triggering a third wave. This warrants action in terms of providing mental health support, especially to those youth who have migrated to another city, away from their home. The stress they face could very well lead to larger problems such as depression and suicidal tendencies. Both the government and non-government organisations working to empower the youth need to work together to address this issue.

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